

1 **ABSTRACT**

2 *This paper proposes a Human Activity Recognition system composed of three modules. The first one*
3 *segments the acceleration signals into overlapped windows and extracts information from each*
4 *window in the frequency domain. The second module detects the performed activity at each window*
5 *using a deep learning structure based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). The first part of this*
6 *structure has several layers associated to each sensor independently and the second part combines the*
7 *outputs from all sensors in order to classify the physical activity. The third module integrates the*
8 *window-level decision in longer periods of time, obtaining a significant performance improvement*
9 *(from 89.83% to 96.62%). These are the best classification results on the PAMAP2 dataset with a*
10 *Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) evaluation.*

1 **CONTENTS**

2 1. Introduction 3
3 2. Methods..... 6
4 2.1. Signal processing 7
5 2.2. Activity classification at window level 10
6 2.3. Post-processing the output of the CNN 14
7 2.4. Evaluation metric and validation 15
8 3. Dataset description 17
9 4. Results and discussion 18
10 4.1. Comparison to previous works using the same dataset 18
11 4.2. Comparison between several deep learning architectures 19
12 4.3. Comparison of post-processing techniques ~~23~~²²
13 4.4. Subject depending analysis 27
14 5. Conclusions 28
15 Acknowledgements 29
16 Abbreviations ~~30~~²⁹
17 References ~~31~~³⁰
18

1 **(BODY OF ARTICLE)**

2 **1. Introduction**

3 Nowadays, the presence of sensors in people's daily lives has increased significantly. Thanks to this
4 increment, it is possible to monitor activities performed by people during daily routine. Using the
5 signals collected by these sensors, computer based systems can supervise, monitor and model human
6 behavior for a wide range of applications. In particular, one important application is the supervision of
7 daily activity ([1], [2], [3]), e.g. exercise monitoring [4] for high-quality training, supervision of the
8 driving style of a person [5] or detection of motor anomalies in Parkinson patients ([6], [7]). Physical
9 activity provides health benefits increasing life expectancy and improving quality of life. Automatic
10 Human Activity Recognition (HAR) helps to measure the physical activity level and check if a person
11 fulfils certain physical activity recommendations, in quantity and quality. This paper focuses on the
12 development of a HAR for physical activity detection.

13
14 HAR can be performed using a wide range of possible sensors. Many of them are increasingly being
15 incorporated in modern commercial devices such as smartphones or smartwatches. Nowadays, these
16 devices include dual cameras, microphones, accelerometers, gyroscopes, etc. Video or microphone
17 recordings raise privacy issues in many scenarios, so inertial sensors are becoming very popular. In the
18 literature, we can find several HAR studies using inertial sensors from smartphones ([8], [9]), and
19 more recently from smartwatches ([10], [11], [12], [13], [14]). Sensors included in these smart devices
20 are less invasive for monitoring human activities but the different wearing locations difficult automatic
21 activity recognition. Monitoring specific physical activities with smart devices is less precise because
22 the detection accuracy depends on the device orientation and location. Therefore, sensors in smart
23 devices would allow a less precise monitoring in training or rehabilitation exercises compared to
24 specific wearable sensors. In this way, these specific wearable devices are being considered to
25 improve athletes' performance or patients' rehabilitation, increasing the accuracy in physical activity
26 recognition [15]. Since these wearable devices are specific for each application, it is necessary to have
27 a system able to be adapted to different sports or rehabilitation protocols, using a different number of

1 sensors. In this paper, specific wearable sensors were used for obtaining high performance in the
2 development of the physical activity recognizer.

3
4 Activity Recognition Chain (ARC) [16] is a general-purpose framework for designing HAR systems
5 using body-worn inertial sensors which segregates the design in several modules, such as feature
6 extraction and activity classification. Regarding the feature extraction module, several features from
7 accelerometer signals have been used both in time and frequency domains. Some of these features
8 were the mean, correlation, signal magnitude area [17] or auto-regression coefficients [18] in time
9 domain and the acceleration energy at different frequency bands [17] or angle between vectors [19] in
10 frequency domain.

11
12 For activity classification, some machine learning approaches have been applied [20]. These
13 approaches include Naïve Bayes [21], Markov Chains [22], Classification and Regression Trees
14 (CART) [23], Support Vector Machines (SVMs) [24] and k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) [25]. Hidden
15 Markov Models (HMMs) have been used for gesture recognition [26], gait recognition [27],
16 transportation mode recognition [28], physical activity detection [29], and activity recognition [30]. In
17 particular, HMMs are effective specifically for activity classification, because they are able to model
18 the time variation of these activities and they have well-understood training algorithms [31].

19
20 Recently, a fast development and advancement of deep learning techniques has made possible to
21 achieve promising accuracies. These deep learning strategies do not need a previous feature extraction
22 module because they can learn features from signals using, for example, Convolutional Neural
23 Networks (CNNs). This way, this type of strategies can be used for both feature learning and activity
24 classification ([32], [33], [34], [35]). In CNNs, convolutional layers, used for feature learning, are
25 combined with a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) for activity classification [36]. All available sensors
26 data are usually joined at the input layer (not specific layers per sensor are considered). Some previous
27 works used raw accelerometer signals ([37], [38]) as inputs to the CNN, and in other cases, the authors
28 considered the signal spectrum [39].

1 In the literature, most of the previous studies divided acceleration signals into overlapped windows,
2 providing a recognized activity per window. However, considering that each activity often lasts more
3 than a unique window, it is interesting to consider a post-processing module to enhance activity
4 classification in longer periods of time. This paper addresses this lack of analysis by developing a
5 HAR system composed of three main modules. The first module segments the acceleration signals into
6 overlapped windows, extracting frequency information from each window. The second module detects
7 the performed activity at each window using a deep learning structure based on CNNs. The third
8 module integrates the window-level decision in longer periods of time, obtaining a significant
9 performance improvement. The main contributions are:

- 10 • The evaluation of several signal transforms to extract frequency information: Fourier and
11 Wavelet transforms.
- 12 • The comparison of several deep learning architectures and the proposal of a new structure based
13 on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) considering sensor independent handling. This
14 structure is composed of two main parts. The first part has several layers associated to each
15 sensor independently and the second part combines the outputs from all sensors in order to
16 classify the physical activity.
- 17 • The comparison and evaluation of several post-processing techniques to integrate the output of
18 the deep learning structure at each window in longer periods of time. Median filtering and
19 Hidden Markov Models (HMMs)-based techniques have been evaluated obtaining a significant
20 improvement in activity recognition accuracy: from 89.83% to 96.62%.

21 This study has been performed using the PAMAP2 dataset [25] using a Leave-One-Subject-Out
22 (LOSO) cross validation. This type of evaluation aims to increase generalization across subjects who
23 are not present in the training set. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this paper presents the best
24 accuracy results (96.62%) on this dataset using a LOSO evaluation.

25 This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the methods used in this study: signal
26 processing, deep learning structure used for activity classification at window level, post-processing
27 techniques and evaluation methodology. Section 3 describes the dataset used as case study. The results

1 and discussion are detailed in section 4. Finally, section 5 summarizes the main conclusions of the
2 paper.

3 2. Methods

4 This section describes the dataset and the three modules composing the HAR (Figure 1):
5 signal processing, activity classification and post-processing.

6

7

FIGURE 1

8

Figure 1. Whole system representation.

9 The signal processing module segments the acceleration signals into overlapped windows and
10 transforms every window from time to frequency domain: Fourier and Wavelet transforms have been
11 considered and compared. The frequency domain provides important information for discriminating
12 between repetitive physical activities (see section 2.1).

13

14 The second module classifies the performed activity at window level using a deep learning structure
15 based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). The proposed architecture is divided into two main
16 parts. The first part includes several convolutional and fully connected layers to process the inputs
17 coming from every sensor independently. These layers allow learning sensor-specific features. The
18 second part is composed of several fully connected layers to combine the information from different
19 sensors and perform the classification task.

20

1 The last module (post-processing) integrates the window-level scores along consecutive windows in
2 order to provide a more robust classification and obtain a better performance. For every window, the
3 deep learning architecture provides a vector with N scores, each one associated to a different activity.
4 The physical activity with the highest score is selected at each window. The post-processing module
5 integrates the score vectors along several consecutive windows before making a decision. For
6 implementing this module, we have considered two alternatives: median filtering and HMMs. Median
7 filtering smooths the consecutive score vectors using several previous and posterior windows. For the
8 HMMs-based approach, we model every activity as a Markov process with unobserved or hidden
9 states. The score vector sequence is the observation chain and the sequence of performed activities is
10 the underlying hidden state chain.

11 **2.1. Signal processing**

12 The acceleration signals were sampled at a rate of 100 Hz. Very unlikely sample losses during
13 acquisition were solved by linear interpolation. These recordings were segmented into analysis
14 windows using the Hamming function. A previous work [25] evaluated several windows lengths
15 concluding that a window length around five seconds is reasonable. This length allows including two
16 or three periods of the periodic movements. Therefore, a window size of 512 samples was selected
17 (5.12 seconds considering a 100 Hz sampling rate) with a shift of one second between consecutive
18 windows. This is the same segmentation used in the baseline study for a better comparison.

19
20 For every window, the Fast Fourier Transform was computed because signals from repetitive activities
21 have relevant information in the frequency domain with the main percentage of energy in low
22 frequencies. On the one hand, the module of the FFT of signals is used due to the significant
23 periodicity observed for several activities ([Figure 2](#)~~Figure-2~~). The FFT module allows us to capture
24 this periodicity, permitting to discriminate sedentary from moderate or vigorous activities. On the
25 other hand, the FFT phase is useful due to its relevant variation with position changes ([Figure 3](#)~~Figure~~
26 ~~3~~).
27

1 Regarding the FFT module of these signals, the energy appears concentrated in low frequencies.
2 Taking into account that we are considering 512 points windows with a 100 Hz sampling rate, we
3 obtain 256 FFT points representing frequencies from 0 to 50 Hz for every window. As in human
4 activities, the energy above 25 Hz is negligible [41], we decided to consider only 128 FFT points that
5 are associated to the spectrogram between 0 and 25 Hz (Figure 2).
6

FIGURE 2

7
8 *Figure 2. FFT module (spectrogram) of X axis acceleration from hand sensor of subject 101.*

8 Regarding the FFT phase, similar to the FFT module, relevant information is concentrated in low
9 frequencies. In this case, our target was keeping the information of the phase for very low frequencies
10 (positional information). This way, we decided to extract only three points of the FFT phase associated
11 to the spectrogram between 0 and 0.6 Hz, as shown in Figure 3. For higher frequencies, the
12 FFT phase shows a noisy behavior.
13

FIGURE 3

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Figure 3. FFT phase of X axis acceleration from hand sensor of subject 101.

In order to complete the analysis, we also computed wavelet coefficients using the Fast Wavelet Transform (FWT). The objective was to see the performance when combining temporal and frequential information. The FWT transform was implemented in an Octave script using the `fwf()` command. We used Daubechies Wavelets [42] with 8 vanishing moments and 5 filterbank iterations.

Figure 4 shows the association between the FFT module with the different activities, including the ground truth with white labels.

FIGURE 4

Figure 4. Activities over FFT module of X axis acceleration from hand sensor of subject 101.

Activities in white text.

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1 In this figure, we show the activities (in white text) over the FFT module. It is possible to distinguish
2 the different activities depending on the energy distribution along the frequencies. For example, we
3 can see how periodic activities such as *walking*, *Nordic walking*, *running* or *rope jumping* generate
4 several harmonics. The *vacuum cleaning* activity shows energy in high frequencies due to the
5 vibration captured by the hand sensor when holding the vacuum cleaner.

6 **2.2. Activity classification at window level**

7 The deep learning architecture proposed in this paper for physical activity recognition is composed of
8 two main parts. The first part has several layers associated to each sensor independently and the
9 second part combines the outputs from the first part of all sensors in order to classify the physical
10 activity. This architecture composed of convolutional and pooling layers to extract features from data
11 in the frequency domain, and fully connected layers to classify those features into one of the
12 performed activities.

13
14 The first part (including sensor dependent layers) is composed of two sub-networks: one for the FFT
15 module and one for the FFT phase. The FFT module subnetwork (~~Figure 5~~Figure-5) receives a 2D
16 input data of 3 (# of axes) x 128 (# of FFT points) size. The first convolutional layer uses 16 kernels
17 with dimensions 3x3 and a Rectified Linear Unit (*ReLU*) activation function. After that, a *Max pooling*
18 *2D layer* with 1x2 pool size and a 0.2 *Dropout layer* are used. Subsequently, a *Flatten layer* is
19 incorporated to form the input to the next two fully connected layers with 128 and 64 neurons
20 respectively. These three fully connected layers use a *ReLU* activation function. ~~Figure 6~~Figure-6
21 represents *ReLU* function, which produces an output equal to 0 when the input is lower than 0 and an
22 output equal to the input when the input is higher or equal to 0. *ReLU* activation function is very
23 interesting because the slope is equal to 1 from 0 to positive infinity. Thanks to that, there is no
24 attenuation of the gradient when being propagated backwards, reducing the vanishing gradient
25 problem.

26 FIGURE 5

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Figure 5. Module CNN architecture.

Figure 6. ReLU function.

The FFT phase subnetwork (Figure 7) receives a 2D input data of 3 (# of axes) x 3 (# of FFT points) size. The first convolutional layer uses 8 kernels with dimension 2x2 and a ReLU activation function. After that, a Max pooling 2D layer with 3x1 pool size and a 0.2 Dropout layer are used. Subsequently, data is connected through a Flatten layer and finally a Dense layer using a ReLU activation function reduces data to 9 features.

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Figure 7. Phase CNN architecture.

1 The weights of these two subnetworks are initialized using two autoencoders, one for the FFT module
2 subnet and the other for the phase subnet. We design every autoencoder including an encoder and a
3 decoder, and we train them in an unsupervised way, trying to reproduce the inputs at the last layer.
4 After training the autoencoders, it is possible to extract, from the intermediate layer, relevant features
5 in the module and phase of the FFT that characterize physical activities. We use the weights of the
6 layers in the encoder part to initialize the weights of the subnetworks described above. This is possible
7 because the encoder part has the same structure than the subnetworks described above for module and
8 phase respectively.

9
10 This way, training the autoencoders in a previous step allows us to get a good initialization point for
11 the weights of these two subnets. One important aspect is that we train only one autoencoder for the
12 FFT module and one for the FFT phase using data from all sensors of different databases ([14], [40])
13 together. This way, we train robust autoencoders integrating information from sensors located in
14 different positions.

15
16 In order to build the deep learning classifier, we create as many module and phase subnets as number
17 of sensors we have in the specific HAR problem. All these subnets are initialized in the same way,
18 using the weights from the encoder part of the two autoencoders trained previously.

19
20 For the second part (after sensor dependent subnets), we concatenate three fully connected layers to
21 reduce data to 64 parameters, with dropout layers for preventing overfitting. These fully connected
22 layers have a *ReLU* activation function. Finally, the last layer is a *Dense layer* with a *softmax*
23 activation function with 12 neurons (one for each activity). ~~Figure 8~~ ~~Figure 8~~ shows the final CNN
24 architecture including the information from three sensors.

25

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FIGURE 8

2

Figure 8. DELAPAR architecture.

3 Thanks to this CNN architecture, the different layers learn high-level features for the module and
 4 phase of each sensor separately (in the first steps) and then, this information is combined in the final
 5 layers of the network. From here on, we name this architecture as DELAPAR (Deep Learning
 6 Architecture for Physical Activity Recognition).

1 2.3. Post-processing the output of the CNN

2 This section describes the use of median filtering and HMMs to post-process the CNN output and
3 increase the robustness of the classification decision, integrating information from contextual
4 windows. For every window, the CNN provides a vector with 12 scores; each score is associated to a
5 different activity. The activity classification at every window is done selecting the activity with the
6 highest score. Post-processing based on median filtering consists of smoothing the consecutive score
7 vectors using several previous and posterior windows.

8
9 For the HMMs-based approach, the main target is to model the scores vector sequence using HMMs.
10 Every activity is represented by a HMM composed of M states (10 states in our case), assuming that
11 every activity can be modelled as a Markov process with unobserved or hidden states. The vector
12 sequence at the CNN output is the observation chain and the sequence of performed activities is the
13 underlying hidden state chain.

14
15 ~~Figure 9~~ Figure-9 shows a representation of the HMMs used in this work, where P_s represents the
16 probability of staying in the same state, P_t represents the probability of transition from state i to state j
17 in the same activity and P_a represents the probability of transition from the last state of one activity to
18 the first state of the same or another activity. Every state has a probability density function (pdf)
19 modelled as linear combination of multivariable Gaussians. We used the software developed in [43]
20 considering the same pdf for all the states in a model, and using diagonal covariance matrix instead of
21 full covariance matrixes because diagonal covariance matrix were better trained with the amount of
22 data available for training in this work.

23

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FIGURE 9

2

Figure 9. HMMs representation.

3 The process of training the HMMs and segmenting the activities is an iterative process consisting of
 4 two steps. Firstly, the HMMs are trained in an unsupervised way using the decision from the CNN.
 5 Secondly, once the HMMs are trained, the vector sequence is re-segmented generating a new
 6 classification decision for every window.

7 **2.4. Evaluation metric and validation**

8 For evaluating the physical recognition performance, we used the classification accuracy and F-
 9 measure metrics as proposed in previous work [25]. The accuracy is defined in equation (1) for a
 10 classification problem of C activities.

$$accuracy = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^C P_{ii} \quad (1)$$

11 Where P_{ij} , is the number of examples of activity i that have been recognized as belonging to activity j ,
 12 C is the number of activities and N is the total number of examples in the testing set. Considering the

1 confusion matrix, the accuracy is the sum of cases in the principal diagonal (number of cases correctly
 2 classified) divided by the total number of examples used in the evaluation.
 3 Regarding F-measure, recall and precision measures are computed using the same equations proposed
 4 in the baseline study [25]:

$$precision = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{i=1}^C \frac{P_{ii}}{R_i} \quad (2)$$

$$recall = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{i=1}^C \frac{P_{ii}}{S_i} \quad (3)$$

$$F - measure = 2 \cdot \frac{precision \cdot recall}{precision + recall} \quad (4)$$

5
 6 Where R_i is the sum of all samples in a column in the confusion matrix, and S_i is the sum of all
 7 samples in a row in the confusion matrix. Given a class C , the precision of this class is the ratio
 8 between examples of C class correctly classified and the total number of examples classified as C
 9 class. Recall is the ratio between examples of C class correctly classified and the actual number of
 10 examples from C class. The global precision and recall are averaged along the C classes. Finally, F-
 11 measure is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. F-measure varies between 1 (perfect precision
 12 and recall) and 0 (worst performance).

13 All metrics results are presented with confidence intervals of 95%, obtained with equation (5) for a
 14 given number of windows (N) [44]. These confidence intervals help us to determine if two
 15 experiments are significantly different (no overlap in the confidence intervals).

$$metric (95\%) = metric \pm 1.96 \sqrt{\frac{metric \cdot (100 - metric)}{N}} \quad (5)$$

16
 17 Regarding the cross-validation strategy used in the experiments, the original work [25] performed a
 18 Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) cross validation procedure using the recordings from one subject for
 19 testing and the data from the rest of the subjects for training. In this paper, a variation of this procedure
 20 has been considered: a cross-validation procedure which uses the data from seven subjects for training,
 21 data from one subject for validation and data from the remaining subject for testing. This configuration

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1 has been repeated nine times in a round-robin strategy. The results presented in this work are average
2 values obtained throughout the nine-fold cross validation procedure. The objective of considering a
3 validation subset (different from the testing subset) is to use this validation subset for adjusting the
4 main parameters of the deep learning neural network. LOSO cross validation procedure aims to
5 increase generalization across subjects who are not present in the training set. This is a more realistic
6 scenario when developing a system for a real application. The activity recognition system is usually
7 adjusted using recordings from subjects different to those subjects that will test the system.

8

9 **3. Dataset description**

10 In this study, we used the Physical Activity Monitoring Data Set (PAMAP2) for physical activity
11 monitoring, which is described in a previous study [25] and available online [40]. This database
12 contains recordings of 12 different physical activities, performed by 9 subjects (1 female and 8 males;
13 27.22 ± 3.31 years and 25.22 ± 2.62 kgm^{-2} of BMI) wearing three Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs)
14 and a heart rate monitor. In our work, only the inertial signals were considered to provide a fair
15 comparison with other previous papers using similar sensors.

16

17 During data collection, IMUs were used as sensors sampling at 100 Hz. A companion unit (a small
18 tablet) was used for data collection, activity labeling and presentation of results. Each IMU contains
19 two 3-axis Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS) accelerometers, a 3-axis MEMS gyroscope,
20 and a 3-axis magneto-resistive magnetic sensor. A human movement can be decomposed in
21 translational and rotational components. Gyroscopes detect angular accelerations related to the
22 rotational component of a movement. On the other hand, accelerometers record lineal accelerations
23 associated to the translational component. In this database, most of the activities showed a more
24 relevant translational component, being more important to discriminate between them. In this work,
25 only signals from the accelerometers were used because they provided a better performance compared
26 to gyroscope measurements in a previous study [14].

27

1 IMUs were placed onto three different body positions: chest, wrist on the dominant arm and ankle on
2 the dominant side. All subjects followed a protocol composed of a minimum of 12 activities or
3 positions when wearing the IMUs (*lying, sitting, standing, walking, running, cycling, Nordic walking,*
4 *ascending stairs, descending stairs, vacuum cleaning, ironing and rope jumping*). These 12 activities
5 are our classification target.

6
7 This dataset is a very good representative of benchmark including activities of daily living because it
8 has a wide variety of activities: from postures like *sitting* and repetitive activities such as *walking* to
9 sport activities like *cycling* and home activities like *ironing*. Additionally, this dataset includes sensors
10 in different locations on the body (chest, wrist and ankle), that allows distinguishing among activities
11 with predominance movement of different limbs.

13 **4. Results and discussion**

14 This section describes the setup of the experiments and the main analyses carried out in this study. The
15 first analysis compares the classification accuracy using the proposed architecture with other deep
16 learning structures proposed in previous works for activity recognition. In the second evaluation, we
17 compare several strategies for integrating information from longer periods of time in the classification
18 decision. The third analysis describes the accuracy depending on the physical characteristics of every
19 subject.

20 **4.1. Comparison to previous works using the same dataset**

21 This section compares the obtained results with those reported in previous works using the same
22 dataset. The first previous work analysed was the baseline work [25], where the authors extracted
23 some hand-crafted features from raw data such as mean, standard deviation or variance and used k-NN
24 as classification algorithm. The authors defined a specific experimental setup: firstly, ten seconds from
25 the beginning and the end of each labelled activity were deleted in order to avoid windows including
26 activity transitions. Secondly, a LOSO 9-fold cross-validation was performed using eight subjects for
27 training and one subject for testing. The system was optimized over the testing set directly.

1 Additionally to the baseline work, we considered other previous works ([20], [34], [35]) using the
 2 same dataset and the same experimental setup. These previous works are very interesting because they
 3 provide a detailed comparison of several strategies including different machine learning techniques
 4 [20] or several deep learning architectures ([34], [35]). ~~Table 1~~ shows the best results reported
 5 in every previous work. For a fair comparison, we replicated these conditions and we evaluated our
 6 deep learning architecture with this original setup (DELAPAR-orig).

7
 8 TABLE 1

Approach	Setup	Test accuracy	F-measure
Baseline system [25]	Original [25]	89.24 ± 0.44 %	91.10 ± 0.40 %
Vote algorithm [20]	Original [25]	85.25 ± 0.50 %	-
attrCNN-IMU [34]	Original [25]	-	90.88 ± 0.40 %
General CNN [35]	Original [25]	91.00 ± 0.40 %	91.16 ± 0.40 %
DELAPAR-orig	Original [25]	93.24 ± 0.35 %	92.73 ± 0.37 %

Table 1. Previous works and DELAPAR-orig approaches results.

9 As shown, previous studies based on deep learning could provide higher performance than the
 10 baseline system (based on k-NN algorithm for activity classification). The deep learning architecture
 11 proposed in this paper (DELAPAR-orig) improved significantly (non-overlap between confidence
 12 intervals) previous results using traditional and deep learning algorithms. The obtained improvement
 13 was more than 2% absolute in accuracy.

15 4.2. Comparison between several deep learning architectures

16 In the literature, there are other interesting deep learning architectures applied to HAR that have not
 17 been evaluated with this dataset. In order to compare our proposal with these deep learning strategies,
 18 we implemented and evaluated some of them. The first one was a Deep Convolutional and Long
 19 Short-Term Memory (LSTM) recurrent neural network (DeepConvLSTM) [38] considering raw data
 20 as inputs to the deep learning algorithm. We also evaluated several types of inputs to our proposal

1 (DELAPAR): wavelet coefficients, values of the FFT module [14] and values of the FFT module and
 2 phase. We analyzed several alternatives with different number of layers. The best results were
 3 obtained using a CNN architecture with fully connected layers (instead of LSTM layers) using the
 4 module and phase of the FFT as inputs to the deep learning architecture (Table 2Table 2).
 5 In the previous section, we used the same experimental setup proposed in the baseline work [25], but
 6 reality does not obey this setup and it is necessary to adopt a more realistic one. For comparing these
 7 deep learning architectures, we considered a LOSO cross-validation with training, validation and
 8 testing subsets. In this evaluation, the configuration of the deep learning structure was optimized over
 9 the validation subset (different to the testing subset). Additionally, the confusing windows in transient
 10 activities were not discarded because they also appear in real applications. This setup is more realistic
 11 and closer to a final application.

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12 TABLE 2

Deep learning structure	Setup	Accuracy	F-measure	Recall	Precision
DeepConvLSTM using raw data as inputs	New	79.78 ± 0.56 %	81.51 ± 0.55 %	80.09 ± 0.56 %	83.13 ± 0.53 %
DELAPAR using Wavelet coefficients	New	88.00 ± 0.46 %	87.04 ± 0.47 %	85.64 ± 0.49 %	88.49 ± 0.45 %
DELAPAR using FFT module	New	88.58 ± 0.45 %	87.52 ± 0.46 %	86.44 ± 0.48 %	88.63 ± 0.45 %
DELAPAR using FFT module and phase	New	89.83 ± 0.43 %	89.79 ± 0.43 %	88.43 ± 0.45 %	91.19 ± 0.40 %

Table 2. Comparison to previous works using CNN architectures.

13 Using raw data was useful for recognizing gestures in previous works [38] that used small analysis
 14 windows (0.5 sec). The sequence of these small windows could be modelled using Recurrent Neural
 15 Networks (RNNs) obtaining good results. For gestures lasting several consecutive windows, LSTMs
 16 layers allowed modelling the temporal evolution of the gesture through these consecutive windows.

1 But the problem when using short windows was that the FFT of these small windows had a bad
2 resolution in the frequency domain, so convolutional layers over the raw data did a better job.

3
4 In the PAMPA2 dataset, we found repetitive physical activities and postures. Repetitive physical
5 activities were composed of periodic movements with relevant information in the frequency domain.
6 In order to have a good FFT resolution in the frequency domain, it was necessary to use longer
7 windows (5.12 sec.) than in previous works, including several repetitions of the same movement.
8 Consecutive windows were very similar because all of them include several repetitions of the same
9 movement. So, in this case, the use of RNNs did not provide any improvement (first row of [Table](#)
10 [2Table-2](#)).

11
12 In order to extract information from the frequency domain, we analysed the FFT module and the
13 wavelet coefficients, obtaining very similar results in both cases (second and third rows of [Table](#)
14 [2Table-2](#)). On the one hand, the wavelet transform allowed gaining temporal information inside every
15 window. On the other hand, the FFT module allowed a better frequency resolution. This resolution
16 was important in several situations. Firstly, this resolution helped to distinguish between activities
17 with a high number of harmonics like walking and running. Secondly, there were postures (like sitting
18 and standing) that showed slow swing movements, better detected with a higher resolution in
19 frequency. [Table 2Table-2](#) shows that there were not statistically significant differences between using
20 wavelet coefficients and using only the FFT module.

21
22 While the FFT module provides information about the frequency of the movement, the FFT phase
23 gives information about postural changes. When considering the FFT phase data as inputs in our CNN
24 architecture (DELAPAR), positional information was helpful to distinguish static activities (like
25 *sitting* or *standing*), also included in this dataset. This is the reason why the use of the FFT module and
26 phase, with longer windows, offered better results in this application (fourth row of [Table 2Table-2](#)).

27

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Table 3 shows the confusion matrix in percentages for DELAPAR using as inputs the FFT module and phase. The rows of confusion matrix refer to real activities (ground truth) and the columns refer to recognized activities. Percentages of 0% are represented with blank cells

TABLE 3

	lying	sitting	standing	walking	running	cycling	Nordic walk	asc. stairs	desc. stairs	vac.clean.	ironing	rope jump.
lying	94.5	0.8	2.9			0.1		0.1		0.7	0.9	
sitting	1.3	84.8	9.6			1.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.9	2.1	
standing	1.1	6.6	86.8	0.2	0.1	0.6	0.4	0.1	0.3	0.6	3.3	
walking		0.1	1.7	96.0			0.3	0.9	0.2	0.1	0.6	
running	0.2	0.3	2.2	0.2	94.5	0.3		0.5	0.4	0.4	0.8	0.1
cycling	0.2	0.6	1.2			95.0	0.1	0.7	0.5	0.8	0.9	
Nordic walk		0.5	0.7	2.9	0.1	0.1	93.9	0.3		0.1	1.6	
asc. stairs	0.2	0.5	4.3	4.0	0.3	0.5	0.7	86.1	0.7	0.4	1.9	0.3
desc. stairs	0.3	2.7	4.5	2.7	0.5	0.9	0.5	4.6	76.8	3.7	2.3	0.5
vac.clean.	1.4	0.5	2.3	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.1	91.5	3.4	0.1
ironing	0.2	1.4	4.7		0.1	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1	6.6	86.1	0.1
rope jump.		2.0	2.5	1.2	1.2	0.4	1.8	1.0	2.0	1.2	9.6	76.9

Table 3. Confusion matrix for DELAPAR using FFT module and phase.

In this confusion matrix, it is possible to observe different groups of activities with high confusability. For example, postures such as *lying*, *sitting* and *standing*, standing activities such as *standing* and *ironing* and walking activities such as *walking*, *ascending stairs* and *descending stairs*. Classification among activities within each of these groups could be confusing because they offer similar behaviour in frequency domain (a strong harmonic structure). However, in this confusion matrix, it is also possible to observe that the system discriminates almost perfectly some pair of activities. For example, *cycling* and *running* could be distinguished very well because cycling activity showed a higher acceleration energy at the ankle sensor compared to the hand sensor, while running showed high energy in all sensors. Another example of good discrimination is *walking* and *running*. These activities showed different fundamental frequency and harmonic structure.

4.3. Comparison of post-processing techniques

For every window, the DELAPAR architecture provides a vector with 12 scores, each one associated to a different activity. The physical activity with the highest score is selected at each window. In order to improve this decision, an additional module has been added after score computation in the *softmax* layer of the DELAPAR architecture. The target of this additional module is to integrate the information from longer periods of time before making a decision. For implementing this module, we have considered two alternatives: a median filter over the score vector sequence and the HMM-based module described in section 2.3. This section compares these two post-processing approaches.

The first approach consists of filtering the sequence of vectors provided by the DELAPAR architecture. We used a median filter including several windows before and after the window under decision. We consider the same number of previous and posterior windows. A study of the number of windows included in the median filter is presented in [Figure 10](#), where we can see the evolution of the final test accuracy depending on the number of contextual windows used in the median filter. The best results are obtained when considering a 61-length filter (30 previous windows, 30 posterior windows and the window under analysis). Considering that we analyse windows with one-second shift, the best results are obtained when integrating in the decision around one minute of signal. As it can be seen in [Figure 10](#), the accuracy initially increases due to the correction of isolated errors (more robust decisions) and then, the performance decreases when we mix several activities in these long periods.

FIGURE 10

Figure 10. Evolution of test accuracy based on filter length.

1 ~~Table 4~~ Table 4 shows the results of the DELAPAR architecture considering the different post-
 2 processing techniques: using the median filter with and without including posterior windows, and
 3 including or not an additional module using HMMs (as described in section 2.3.). For comparison, the
 4 results without post-processing are also showed.

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TABLE 4

Post-processing approach	Test accuracy		F-measure		Recall		Precision	
	No HMMs	HMMs						
No post-processing	89.83 ± 0.43 %	91.70 ± 0.39 %	89.79 ± 0.43 %	92.17 ± 0.38 %	88.43 ± 0.45 %	91.70 ± 0.39 %	91.19 ± 0.40 %	92.64 ± 0.37 %
Median filter using only previous windows	91.94 ± 0.38 %	92.48 ± 0.37 %	91.79 ± 0.39 %	92.76 ± 0.36 %	90.36 ± 0.42 %	92.48 ± 0.37 %	93.26 ± 0.35 %	93.04 ± 0.36 %
Median filter using previous and posterior windows	96.62 ± 0.25 %	96.34 ± 0.26 %	96.04 ± 0.27 %	96.37 ± 0.26 %	96.09 ± 0.27 %	96.34 ± 0.26 %	95.99 ± 0.28 %	96.39 ± 0.26 %

Table 4. Comparison of different filtering strategies.

1 As it can be seen, a post-processing with the appropriate length increases significantly the
2 performance of our system. This improvement has been due to the reduction of isolated errors.

3 ~~Figure 11~~ ~~Figure 11~~ shows the evolution of the real activity performed (in blue) and the prediction (in
4 red) for a set of test samples from *subject 103* when no post-processing is applied. In this figure it is
5 possible to see that the subject performed *lying (1)*, *sitting (2)* and *standing (3)* activities subsequently.
6 However, the system's prediction without post-processing has some isolated mistakes during each
7 physical activity.

8
9

FIGURE 11

10

Figure 11. Real activity and prediction without the median filter.

11 On the contrary, ~~Figure 12~~ ~~Figure 12~~ shows the same sequence of activities as ~~Figure 11~~ ~~Figure 11~~ but
12 when incorporating a median filter in the score vector sequence before the final decision. In this
13 figure, it is possible to see that fewer isolated errors appeared once the post-processing filter is applied.

14

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1

FIGURE 12

2

Figure 12. Real activity and prediction with post-processing using a median filter.

3 As it can be seen in the figures when using a median filter, the classification decision is smoothed and
4 these isolated errors disappear.

5 When using only previous windows in the median filtering, we obtained a significant improvement
6 (second row of [Table 4Table-4](#)), but this is smaller compared to the case of using previous and
7 posterior windows (third row of [Table 4Table-4](#)). The main advantage of not using posterior windows
8 is that there is not an additional delay in the system decision. When this delay is not important, using
9 previous and posterior windows provides better results.

10 Applying the HMMs module only significantly improves the accuracy when no post-processing
11 approach is applied. When using the median filter, the HMMs module does not contribute to improve
12 the performance additionally. As the HMMs-based module needs the output of the classifier for all
13 windows (to train the HMMs), this type of post-processing cannot be used in applications where a
14 small delay between activity performing and detection is required.

15 When including posterior windows in the median filter, a delay in the system response is introduced.
16 One second of delay is added for each subsequent window included in the filtering. In order to reduce
17 this delay, we also evaluate the median filter using only previous windows.

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Table 5 shows the confusion matrix for DELAPAR when median filter using previous and posterior windows post-processing technique is applied (the best result obtained in the paper). In this confusion matrix, it is possible to observe that the majority of isolated errors have disappeared and the classification decision has been smoothed thanks to the post-processing technique as shown in Figure 12.

TABLE 5

	lying	sitting	standing	walking	running	cycling	Nordic walk	asc. stairs	desc. stairs	vac.clean.	ironing	rope jump.
lying	97.3	0.5								2.2		
sitting	0.5	94.9	4.5									
standing		4.3	94.5					0.5			0.7	
walking				99.2	0.1	0.4		0.3				
running					98.8	0.9	0.2					0.2
cycling				0.1	0.3	99.1	0.5					
Nordic walk					0.4	99.4	0.3					
asc. stairs					0.5	0.6	97.4	1.0	0.5			
desc. stairs				0.4	14.8	0.3	1.2	82.7	0.5			0.1
vac.clean.			0.5					0.3		98.4	0.8	
ironing		0.1	1.8						0.1	98.0		
rope jump.				4.7				1.8		9.8	83.6	

Table 5. Confusion matrix for DELAPAR including median filter using previous and posterior windows.

4.4. Subject depending analysis

As the physical characteristics of the different subjects are available, we can compute the correlations between subjects' physical characteristics and the recognition accuracy obtained for each subject. Regarding the DELAPAR architecture without filtering (89.83 ± 0.43 % of accuracy), Pearson correlation coefficients between height and test accuracy ($\rho_{H,TA}$), between weight and test accuracy ($\rho_{W,TA}$) and between Body Mass Index (BMI) and test accuracy ($\rho_{BMI,TA}$) are $\rho_{H,TA} = 0.52$ (p -value = 0.1514), $\rho_{W,TA} = 0.76$ (p -value = 0.0171) and $\rho_{BMI,TA} = 0.49$ (p -value = 0.1773) respectively. In all cases, we obtained a positive correlation between these three variables and the test

1 accuracy, being the subject weight the variable with a significant correlation ($p - value < 0.05$). A
2 bigger dataset would be necessary to provide a deeper analysis and obtain more significant
3 conclusions.

4
5 Another important observation is related to the subject with the lowest BMI: *subject 106*. If we
6 analyse the FFT module for all subjects and activities, we see that *subject 106* provides the highest
7 values of energy from hand and chest sensors in activities with higher physical intensity, such as
8 *running* and *cycling*. For example, [Figure 13](#) shows this fact for the hand sensor during the
9 *running* activity. The *subject 106* is represented in orange colour.

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11 FIGURE 13

12 *Figure 13. Average FFT module of X axis from hand sensor for the running activity.*

13 5. Conclusions

14 This paper has presented a HAR system composed of three main modules. The first module segments
15 the acceleration signals into overlapped windows and extracts information from the frequency domain.
16 The second module detects the performed activity at each window by using a deep learning

1 architecture based on CNNs. This architecture is composed of two main parts. The first part has
2 several layers for each sensor independently and the second part combines the outputs from the first
3 part of all sensors to classify the physical activity. This new CNNs architecture constitutes a sensor-
4 independent approach where high-level features for each sensor can be learned separately. The inputs
5 to these sensor dependent layers are the FFT module and phase from the three acceleration axes x, y
6 and z. The main advantage of this architecture is the fact that it is opened to easily include data from
7 new sensors adding additional layers without modifying the main structure.

8
9 In a window-based activity classification, this deep learning structure improved significantly (non-
10 overlap between confidence intervals) previous results using traditional and deep learning over the
11 same dataset algorithms. When applying post-processing techniques over the score vector sequence,
12 isolated classification errors were reduced obtaining an important accuracy improvement from 89.83%
13 to 96.62% (the best accuracy results on PAMAP2 dataset using a LOSO evaluation).

14
15 We have also included a preliminary correlation analysis between the accuracy and subjects' physical
16 characteristics. A deeper analysis over a bigger dataset would be necessary to develop strategies that
17 allow adapting the deep learning architecture to specific physical characteristics of every subject. This
18 is the study we will consider for future work.

19
20 Additionally, we will increase the amount of data to train the autoencoder weights including sensor
21 signals from additional databases. This aspect will allow us to pre-train weights with a high range of
22 variability of physical activities and subjects.

23

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6 researchers who kept the records and developed the PAMAP Data Set.

7

8 **Abbreviations**

9 ARC: Activity Recognition Chain

10 BMI: Body Mass Index

11 CART: Classification and Regression Trees

12 CNNs: Convolutional Neural Networks

13 DELAPAR: Deep Learning Architecture for Physical Activity Recognition

14 DNN: Deep Neural Network

15 FFT: Fast Fourier Transform

16 HAR: Human Activity Recognition

17 HMMs: Hidden Markov Models

18 IMUs: Inertial Measurement Units

19 k-NN: k-Nearest Neighbors

20 LOSO: Leave-One-Subject-Out

21 LSTM: Long Short-Term Memory

22 MEMS: Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems

23 MLP: Multi-Layer Perceptron

24 PAMAP2: Physical Activity Monitoring Data Set

25 ReLU: Rectified Linear Unit

26 RNNs: Recurrent Neural Networks

27 SVMs: Support Vector Machines

1

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3

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FIGURES

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TABLES